

FORMING LIBRARY CULTURE IN THE FAMILY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11195817>

Abstract: In this article, the current state of the reading culture, which is of incomparable importance for the ideological and ideological development of young people in our society, some problems in this regard and opinions on their elimination, as well as the role of books in educating the young generation with spiritual and intellectual potential in our country. The incomparability of books, the attention paid to them, and the issues of developing family reading by promoting the ways and means of making the child interested in books in the family are described.

Key words: reading culture, child, family, interest in books, spiritual intellectual, well-rounded person, communicative.

“As we have set ourselves the lofty goals of establishing the foundation of the third renaissance, we must create the environment and conditions that will nurture new Khorezms, Berunis, Ibn Sinas, Ulugbeks, Navai and Baburs”¹.

Today, in our country, special attention is paid to the formation of a culture of reading, which is of incomparable importance in raising the spiritual-intellectual potential of the young generation, their thinking and worldview, and in raising a well-rounded person who lives with love and loyalty to the Motherland and its people.

The 21st century is going down in history as the age of innovative technologies, when scientific and technical progress is rapidly developing, the pace of using information and communication tools is increasing sharply, and material resources that satisfy the demands, needs and goals of citizens are being produced in sufficient quantities. The material and technical equipment necessary for a happy and prosperous life of mankind is being improved, polished, and more convenient day by day, year by year. The development of our country and the well-being of our people, "regardless of nationality, language and religion, people live freely, peacefully and prosperously, live contentedly with today's life"², making sure that the future of the country is guaranteed is the main goal of the rational and fair policy of our country. . After all, Uzbekistan, as

¹ “O‘zbekiston Respublikasiga axborot-kutubxona xizmati ko‘rsatishni yanada takomillashtirish to‘g‘risida”gi O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yil 7- iyundagi PQ-4354-sonli Qarori.

² O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning Oliy Majlisga Murojaatnomasi. – “Zarafshon”, 2018-yil 29- dekabr, 155-156-son.

our head of state admitted, is rapidly moving from national recovery to national growth.

It is known from the life experience of our people that our ancestors paid special attention to reading books in the upbringing of children. The spirituality of our scholars and creators, crown princes and geniuses such as Great Navoi-u Babur, Amir Temur-u Ulug'bek, was formed by loving books from childhood. Our ancestors enriched the world of imagination and thinking, the world of spirituality by listening to folk tales and epics. Literary masterpieces - whether they are examples of folk oral creativity or written works - love and loyalty to the country, mother tongue, family, compatriots, national pride, honor, justice and fairness in the hearts of our people. served as the main tool in the formation of the qualities of respect, nobility and generosity. Such masterpieces of spirituality were read, listened to, and most importantly, discussed in the family circle or in the community, based on debates and arguments, the essence of the works was understood and understood.

It is important that in such circles, in which young and old participate with equal interest, the ability to observe and reason, think logically, have a broad worldview and thinking is formed, faith and will are strengthened, oratory skills grow, people's minds also have meaning, He became rich both spiritually and intellectually. Today, in many households, almost no time is devoted to family reading. In most families, the owner of the house is always busy with work, so after dinner, they either sit down next to the window to write about the tiredness of the day, or they prefer to sleep to relax. There are even families where parents themselves prefer to spend time at home with their phone or computer rather than with their child. Instead of putting up with their children's whims, being emotionally close to them, and taking an interest in their achievements and problems, their studies are entrusted to their teachers or only their mastery of academic subjects is monitored, education and upbringing , will be mainly the work of teachers and trainers in educational institutions.

For the rest of the day, the child who is left alone or unsupervised mainly prepares an independent lesson. he spends most of his time, but he spends his days not understanding the essence of the shows he has watched and the knowledge he has learned. The saddest thing is that nowadays, most of the young people are playing entertainment games that have a strong place in the memory of various types of mobile communication devices or computer equipment (even more terrible - most of these games have a lot of scenes of shooting, murder, fighting, drunkenness), through the Internet. are those who

have downloaded but are becoming ardent fans of movies and photos that are not appropriate for their age.

If a child does not know how to read something, if he does not listen to what he reads, or if he does not understand the essence, then he cannot get any knowledge and pleasure from it, so he cannot get any aesthetic pleasure and spiritual energy from such illicit games, on the contrary, thoughtfulness, A number of other negative vices such as irritability, nervousness, indifference, indifference, irresponsibility, laziness, aimlessness are formed and become more and more firmly established in the psyche and character. A great scholar, a true patriot, a teacher with high potential, Najmiddin Kubro, said, "I saw success in effort, and failure in indifference and laziness." Therefore, the heads of the family should not pay attention to the fate of the children, start reading age-appropriate books with the children and hold family conversations about the works read, the knowledge gained, their place and importance in human life, they should pay more attention to listening to the opinions of their sons and daughters, support them, and correct their shortcomings gently and gently.

This situation helps not only in the development of book-loving children in the family, but also in the formation of a friendly atmosphere among family members, in strengthening the feelings of respect for parents and self-confidence, instilling thoughtfulness, responsibility, accountability, it also serves as a unique foundation in cultivating the qualities of frugality, valuing time, striving to become a necessary person for nature and society, the country.

Along with the library and information service, the family, neighborhood, education system, labor unions, state power, political parties, public organizations, mass media and other institutions of civil society are important factors in the formation of reading culture. There is a saying that "a bird does what it sees in its nest", a child is formed by the influence of the family and the direct participation of family members. Because the child spends most of his time in the family. Family is the center of education and spirituality. If the family is enlightened, then the child growing up in it will learn from it. It is very important to introduce children to our national values and rich culture, to form aesthetic education in them. It is impossible to understand the national identity and the feeling of national pride without deep knowledge of the centuries-old values, huge, rich and cultural heritage of our people. Such high feelings are formed in the hearts of our young people through their love for books. A child is a great blessing. The grace of human life, the fulfillment of dreams, its bright

future. Life without children is not good for anyone. For every parent, a child is more dear and proud with his manners, discipline, and spiritual maturity.

In short, teaching the cultural wealth created by our nation, especially the Holy Qur'an and Hadith Sharif, which educates young people in the spirit of human virtues, serves as an important tool in the education of young people and their development into mature individuals. There is no doubt that the children brought up in such families will become followers of our great grandfathers - Khorezms, Berunis, Ibn Sinas, Ulugbeks, Navoi and Babur, who will serve for the development of our country in the future.

Therefore, every parent should pay special attention to the education of their child not only physically, but also intellectually, mentally, and spiritually, provide them with art books suitable for their age, exchange ideas with them about the books they read, should be encouraged.

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